

ORGANIZATION OF THE LESSON PROCESS IN NEW STYLES BY TEACHERS IN MUSIC CULTURE LESSONS IN UNIVERSAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the influence of music on people's lives, the influence of music in educating young people as a perfect person, the organization of new styles by the use of various methods by teachers of music culture in general education schools.

Keywords: music, interest, cultural event, lesson, habit, tradition, person, teacher, development, student, style.

UMUMTA'LIM MAKTABLARIDAGI MUSIQA MADANIYATI DARSLARIDA O'QITUVCHILAR TOMONIDAN DARS JARAYONINI YANGICHA USLUBLARDA TASHKIL ETISH

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola musiqaning insonlarning hayotiga ta'siri, yoshlarni komil inson sifatida tarbiyalashda musiqaning ta'siri, umumta'lim maktablarida faoliyat yuritayotgan musima madaniyati o'qituvchilar tomonidan turli xil me'todlardan foydalanish orqali yangi uslublarni tashkil qilish haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: musiqa, qiziqish, madaniy tadbir, dars, odat, an'ana, inson, o'qituvchi, rivojlanish, o'quvchi, uslub.

ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ УЧЕБНОГО ПРОЦЕССА В НОВЫХ СТИЛЯХ УЧИТЕЛЯМИ НА УРОКАХ МУЗЫКАЛЬНОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ В ОБЩЕОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ШКОЛАХ

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Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о влиянии музыки на жизнь людей, влиянии музыки на воспитание молодежи как совершенной личности, организации новых стилей путем использования различных методов учителями музыкальной культуры в общеобразовательных школах. .

Ключевые слова: музыка, интерес, культурное мероприятие, урок, привычка, традиция, человек, педагог, развитие, ученик, стиль.

Music is one of the most important and complex aspects in the development of human personality, which occupies a large place in our cultural life, and teaches to correctly perceive and appreciate the beautiful things around.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1].

In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom",

of May 30, 2019 “ On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3].

Music shapes a person’s view of high taste. Music has the ability to have a strong influence on human life, and is an important means of introducing students to the world of sophistication and moral and ideological education. The grandfather of our national culture, Abu Nasr Al Farabi, said about this science: “Music is a companion of the human soul”. Music is a means of active development of emotional feelings that affects a person quickly. Music is an integral part of the human psyche. Education of music culture, which is a component of human spirituality, is the main goal of music education. In order to realize this high goal, the duties of the music teacher are as follows;

- To increase students’ love and interest in the art of music.
- Development of artistic creativity and feelings during musical activities.
- Ethical and aesthetic education of students through the artistic and ideological content of the taught works.
- In musical culture classes, it is necessary to do things such as instilling enthusiasm in students about the profession and cocktail. [4].

A music teacher should have sufficient knowledge, skills and experience in the theoretical and practical fields of music art, that is, he should also work as an instrumentalist, singer, choir director, accompanist, music theorist and practitioner. it is necessary. Organization of music culture in general education schools, effective teaching of music and singing in a new style is still not up to the demand in some places. Due to the lack of highly educated music teachers in general education schools, in some schools the subject of music culture is considered a secondary subject and given to teachers of other subjects. As a result, students are not satisfied with this subject.

They face many difficulties in entering universities in this field. The role of some music teachers is indispensable in preventing and eliminating these issues. Education of students in universities is currently in high demand. As the teaching process plays an important role in teaching students musical literacy and making them perfect specialists in musical fields, education is one of the main tasks along with education.

Each teacher plays an important role in making the lesson interesting, using advanced technological methods, and organizing the lesson in a modern way. It is appropriate for a teacher to constantly work on his profession to improve his professional skills, to create independently and to inculcate students in the direction of teacher-student. It is necessary to increase the interest of students in the institute and students in the school and prevent them from getting bored. There are also cases where some teachers are bored by students from their classes, and students at school are bored with the lessons, and they withdraw from the deep mastery of this field.

Of course, in order to prevent this, the teacher should work tirelessly on himself and be creative. He should strengthen his qualifications and skills. It is certain that any teacher who has graduated from the university will start his career in the secondary school in the future. We, the teachers of the Pedagogical Institute, taking into account the above, correctly, clearly

and clearly explain to university students how to start a lesson in a general education school and how to teach it effectively in lectures, independent work processes, laboratory classes. we must give. [5].

With some students, it is necessary to work individually with students at school. In this regard, it is necessary to organize extracurricular activities. It is appropriate to make pupils or students sing according to their voice ranges, identifying their voice ranges in the course of the lesson and extracurricular processes. Of course, it is advisable to constantly adjust the volume before singing.

In the institute, it would be appropriate to select the works of the students according to the vocal range of each performer, dividing their voices into bass, baritone, tenor, alto, soprano, etc. Personally, I organize an extracurricular club and use the works of great composers, poets and composers, as well as my own songs. So that our students will work with children more in the future.

They should know well the process of the lesson, that is, how to develop the lesson of music culture. Nowadays, in some schools, the lesson of music culture cannot be said to be done correctly. The reason for this is that the teacher who teaches that subject is not an expert or has not mastered playing a musical instrument. As a result, only when children are told to write a poem and memorize it at home, students evaluate their knowledge based on that. This is like a literature lesson. However, the parts of music theory, singing in a choir, and listening to music are left incomplete. Some teachers record ready-made songs on tape recorders or mobile phones and play them to the students, forcing the students to sing along to the song. However, the range of children's voices does not match the song recorded on the tape. This is definitely a mistake. In my opinion, every music teacher must be able to play an instrument perfectly. With that instrument, it is appropriate to tune children's voices and sing children in a live performance.

The lesson of music culture must be divided into three parts.

Part 1: Music Theory.

Part 2: Singing in chorus.

Part 3: Listening to music.

In the first part, that is, about 8-10 minutes are devoted to music literacy, about 22-25 minutes to the second part, and 7-8 minutes to the third part. If there is more time, what has been learned is repeated and reinforced, and children's knowledge is assessed and homework is given. [6].

In addition to the above, it is necessary to say in addition to what has been said in order to make the lesson of music culture more understandable and interesting, first of all, before starting the lesson, you should greet and take notes, and briefly ask them to evaluate the previous lesson in terms of music literacy. after that, it will be appropriate to start a new topic and give an understanding of music theory, and then adjust the children's voice.

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